

THE QUALITY OF INSTRUCTION AND SERVICES AS PREDICTORS OF RE-ENROLLMENT INTENT AMONG GRADE 7-9 STUDENTS IN A PRIVATE CATHOLIC SCHOOL IN DAVAO CITY

Moxie Jualianne Abucayon¹, Nikka Joy Araza¹, Sheena Marie Gargar¹, Alexie Haspe¹, Earl Jun Roma¹, Emmanuel L. Templa, MPA²

¹ Senior High School Department, St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc., Toril, Davao City, Philippines

² Research and Publication- Basic Education Office, St. Peter's College of Toril Inc, Toril, Davao City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between instructional quality, institutional services, and the re-enrollment intentions of Junior High School students at a private Catholic school in Davao City. The research aims to assess how teaching effectiveness, content relevance, assessment quality, and service quality influence students' decisions to continue their enrollment. Using a descriptive correlational design, data were gathered through a structured survey from a sample of students. Statistical methods, including mean scores, Pearson correlation, and linear regression, were employed to analyze the relationships and predict the impact of instructional and service quality on re-enrollment intentions. Findings indicate a positive perception of instructional quality, with teacher effectiveness rated highest. However, response variability highlights areas for improvement, particularly in adapting teaching methods. Instructional quality was found to moderately predict re-enrollment intentions, while service quality also showed a moderate positive correlation, underscoring the importance of high-quality institutional services. The study concludes that instructional and service quality are critical to student retention. Recommendations include enhancing faculty development programs, improving service responsiveness, and fostering a student-centered learning environment to promote re-enrollment and student loyalty.

Keywords: *Instructional Quality, Service Quality, Reenrollment Intention, Private Catholic School, Quantitative Correlational Study*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental pillar of individual and societal development, with schools playing a crucial role in equipping students with the knowledge and skills necessary for academic and personal growth. However, the decision to enroll and continue enrollment in a school is influenced by various factors. Among these, the quality of instruction and the effectiveness of institutional services significantly shape students' educational experiences and decisions. Therefore, this study examines the relationship between instructional quality, institutional services, and the re-enrollment intentions of Junior High School students.

Many studies and related literature have explored the influence of the quality of instruction and services on students' intent to re-enroll in a school.

For instance, in the global setting, a gap often exists between students' expectations and the quality of service and instruction provided by educational institutions. This misalignment frequently results in dissatisfaction with various aspects of school management, including the learning experience and support services (Tupari et al., 2023). Student dissatisfaction is a pressing concern, as it reflects potential shortcomings in the educational process and may impact academic motivation and institutional commitment (Abasimi & Xiaosong, 2016; Austin & Pervaiz, 2017). Landrum et al. (2021) emphasized that student satisfaction is closely linked to instructional effectiveness and service quality, contributing to long-term student engagement. Similarly, Qureshi et al. (2021) stressed the need for innovative approaches to enhance educational services and teaching strategies to meet the evolving expectations of 21st-century learners.

Ensuring high-quality instruction and services is fundamental for student retention and a competitive advantage for educational institutions (Ramovš & Milfelner, 2023). In evaluating service quality, key performance indicators help determine whether educational institutions meet established standards and adequately fulfill students' needs (Deng et al., 2023). These assessments allow institutions to refine their instructional approaches and service frameworks, ultimately fostering more significant student commitment and increasing re-enrollment rates. Similar trends are evident in the Philippine education system, where factors such as institutional reputation and service quality play a crucial role in students' decisions to remain enrolled.

In the Philippine context, the availability of numerous educational options has made instructional quality and service excellence distinguishing factors for attracting and retaining students (De Ramos & Briones, 2024). Gadian et al. (2020) identified student satisfaction as a key determinant of institutional preference and long-term enrollment. Ang (2023) further argued that positive student experiences with instruction and services

enhance re-enrollment intentions, as satisfied students exhibit stronger loyalty to their institutions. This is supported by Ong et al. (2023), who emphasized that student commitment drives higher retention rates and leads to active advocacy for the institution. Moreover, research has highlighted the role of institutional reputation and perceived service quality in shaping student loyalty, particularly in private colleges (Murcia & Miralles, 2016). Enilo and Ortega (2023) similarly found that students in Mindanao prioritize quality services when making enrollment decisions, reinforcing the importance of service excellence in student retention.

Despite extensive research on re-enrollment determinants in higher education, there remains a significant gap in understanding how instructional quality and service delivery specifically influence junior high school students' re-enrollment intentions in private Catholic institutions, such as the institution where the study is conducted. Existing literature has primarily focused on broader factors affecting student retention, often overlooking the perspectives of younger learners and the unique challenges they face in decision-making regarding continued enrollment.

This study seeks to address this gap by examining the key predictors of re-enrollment among junior high school students (Grades 7 to 9) in the research locale. The primary goal is to explore how instruction and service quality influence students' intent to re-enroll in the institution. Furthermore, this study aims to explore which of the two variables, quality of instruction and service, significantly influences the intention of students to re-enroll. By doing so, the study aims to provide actionable recommendations for enhancing instructional strategies and institutional services, ultimately contributing to a more student-centered educational experience and reinforcing institutional sustainability.

Research Questions

This study examines the quality of instructions and services as predictors of re-enrollment intent among grade 7-9 students in a Private Catholic School in Davao City for the school year 2024-2025. It seeks to determine the correlation between the quality of instructions and students' interest in re-enrollment and investigate the influence of the quality of services on students' interest in re-enrollment.

Additionally, the study aims to identify which variable, quality of instruction or quality of services, strongly influences the intent to re-enroll among students. Specifically, this study answers the following research question:

1. What is the perceived quality of instruction for Grade 7-9 students? Specifically in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Teaching Effectiveness
 - 1.2 Content Relevance
 - 1.3 Assessment Quality
2. What is the perceived quality of services for Grade 7-9 students? Specifically in terms of the following:

- 2.1 Learning Environment
- 2.2 Physical Infrastructure and Facilities
- 2.3 Responsiveness

- 3. What is the student's interest in re-enrolling in the next school year?
- 4. Is there a significant influence on the quality of instructions on grade 7-9 students' interest in the intent to re-enroll?
- 5. Is there a significant influence on the quality of services on grade 7-9 students' interest in the intent to re-enroll?

Hypotheses:

In the conduct of this study, the following research hypothesis is advanced and tested according to a 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1 = There is no significant relationship between the quality of instructions and re-enrollment among Grade 7-9 students.

Ha1 = There is a significant relationship between the quality of instructions and re-enrollment among Grade 7-9 students.

Ho2= There is no significant relationship between the quality of services and re-enrollment among Grade 7-9 students.

Ha2= There is a significant relationship between the quality of services and re-enrollment among Grade 7-9 students.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive correlational design, to examine the relationships between variables (Bhat, 2023). A descriptive correlational approach enables the collection and analysis of data from at least two variables to determine whether a statistical relationship exists between them. To achieve its objectives, this study utilized correlational analysis. This non-experimental method examines the degree of association between the independent variables (quality of instruction and quality of services) and the dependent variable (re-enrollment) (Devi et al., 2022). Furthermore, linear regression analysis was employed to establish the predictive relationship between these variables (Taylor, 2024). This research design was deemed appropriate as it facilitates the identification of causal relationships through mathematical, computational, and statistical techniques. Survey questionnaires were used to collect numerical data, ensuring precise measurement of the relationship between variables and providing empirical evidence to support the study's findings.

Research Locale

This study will be conducted in a Private Catholic School at McArthur Highway, Crossing Bayabas, Toril, Davao City, Philippines. The school offers services from pre-kindergarten to college. The Junior High School (JHS) Department at SPCT, catering to

Grades 7 to 10, is PAASCU Accredited Level II. It aims to produce graduates who are self-directed evangelized-evangelizers, demonstrate competence across disciplines in preparation for college, and are responsive to diverse community concerns. The institution was chosen because of the researcher's affiliation and access to the target respondents within the JHS program.

Participants

This study employed the stratified sampling method to identify respondents, which divides a population into smaller subgroups known as strata (Hayes, 2021). This technique is best for the study because it avoids bias and ensures proper representation. The researchers will identify 70% of the total population of 349 Grade 7-9 students, resulting in a sample of 243 students from research locale. for the school year 2024 to 2025 as research respondents of the study, with 79 students (32%) from Grade 7, 80 students (33%) from Grade 8, and 85 students (35%) from Grade 9. The 243 samples are sufficient to statistically compute the data that will be gathered in preparation for answering the questions and problems raised in this study.

Instruments of the Study

This study used an adapted-modified research instrument for data collection, assessing students' perceptions of instructional quality, school services, and their intent to re-enroll. The instrument contained a letter explaining the study's purpose and a structured questionnaire. It evaluated aspects of teacher effectiveness (Calaguas, 2012), content relevance (Tolentino et al., 2020; Williams et al., 2008), assessment quality (Leeuwenkamp et al., 2018), and the learning environment (McGhee et al., 2007). It also examined the impact of physical infrastructure (Sosibo & Cape Peninsula University of Technology, 2019) and institutional responsiveness (Manogura et al., 2021), along with factors influencing re-enrollment (The Institute for Habits of Mind, 2022). The instrument was validated by three experts in education and research, leading to adjustments based on their feedback.

Data Analysis

The data analysis utilized several statistical tools. Mean Score and Standard Deviation were used to address Problems 1, 2, and 3, providing detailed insights into the sample and its variability (Andrade, 2020). For Problems 4 and 5 and Hypotheses Ho1 and Ho2, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied to examine the strength and direction of the relationship between quantitative variables (McClenaghan, 2024). Finally, linear regression was used to analyze further problems 4 and 5 and test hypotheses Ho1 and Ho2, determining the effect of the quality of instruction and services on students' intent to re-enroll. This method assesses the relationship between variables (Kumari & Yadav, 2018).

Procedure

The researchers undertook several steps to gather data for this study. To begin, the researchers obtained a list of Grade 7-9 High School students for the 2023-2024 academic year from the registrar's office to identify potential respondents. They then requested permission from the adviser of the high school students of the school. to conduct a study about "Quality of Instruction and Quality of Services as Predictors of Re-Enrollment Intent among Grade 7-9 students at St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc." After receiving approval, the researchers gave the respondents questionnaires, making sure they were clear and helpful in preserving data integrity and reducing biases. Following approval, the researchers administered questionnaires to the selected respondents, ensuring clarity, maintaining data integrity, and minimizing biases. After collecting the questionnaires, the researchers meticulously tabulated the results, organizing and summarizing the data using statistical tools or software. Visual aids, such as graphs and charts, were employed to enhance clarity and understanding. Finally, the researchers crafted a research paper, synthesizing the study's purpose, methodology, results, and conclusions into a cohesive narrative. They adhered to academic standards to ensure credibility and contribute meaningfully to existing knowledge.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings and discussion derived from the study on the quality of instruction and services as predictors of re-enrollment intent among grade 7–9 students in a private catholic school in Davao City. The results are organized into distinct categories: (1) the level of the perceived quality of instruction for Grade 7-9 students, (2) the level of the perceived quality of services for Grade 7-9 students, (3) the level of the student's interest in re-enrolling in the next school year, and (4) correlation and regression analyses examining the relationships among key variables. Each category is analyzed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how the quality of instruction and quality of services of the school influences the re-enrollment intent among the students.

Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction for Grade 7-9 Students

The following table shows the result of each indicator's question/statement concerning the Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction variable for Grade 7-9 Students. The results are as follows:

Table 1: Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction for Grade 7-9 Students: Teacher Effectiveness

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Teacher Effectiveness			
My teachers give activities that help develop critical thinking.	3.80	0.93	HIGH

My teachers adjust their teaching style to fit different student needs.	3.60	1.00	HIGH
My teachers immediately explain the parts of lessons that are unclear to me.	3.63	1.04	HIGH
My teachers use creative ways to teach lessons.	3.76	0.99	HIGH
My teachers give many examples to make complex topics easier to understand.	3.79	0.97	HIGH
Indicator Mean	3.71	0.99	HIGH

The data in Table 1 shows that students generally perceive their teachers as effective in delivering quality instruction, with an overall mean score of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.99. The highest-rated statement, "My teachers give activities that help develop critical thinking" (M = 3.80, SD = 0.93), reflects students' appreciation for activities that enhance critical thinking, aligning with Tian et al. (2024), who found such exercises improve both engagement and academic performance. However, the statement "My teachers adjust their teaching style to fit different student needs" received a lower mean score of 3.60 (SD = 1.00), suggesting that while teaching effectiveness is generally high, there is room for improvement in differentiated instruction.

These findings indicate that while teachers are primarily successful in engaging students, there is an opportunity to tailor teaching strategies better to accommodate individual learning needs. The variation in perceptions, as reflected in the standard deviation, suggests some inconsistency in student experiences. Blömeke and Kaiser (2017) argue that adapting teaching methods to diverse learning styles is essential for fostering inclusivity, while Mwirigi and Muthaa (2015) emphasize that a responsive approach enhances student satisfaction and retention. This reinforces the need for greater flexibility in teaching practices.

In light of these results, improving instructional responsiveness could enhance both the learning experience and students' intent to re-enroll. As suggested by Nguyen and Nguyen (2016), investing in teacher professional development to refine inclusive teaching strategies is crucial. Schweig (2019) also emphasizes the importance of ongoing professional growth for teachers to effectively meet students' evolving needs. Focusing on personalized instruction will ultimately help ensure academic success and long-term retention.

Table 2: Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction for Grade 7-9 Students: Content Relevance

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Content Relevance			
The lessons presented aligned with the topics and skills required by the learning competencies.	3.86	0.84	HIGH
The lessons and activities connect to real-world situations that help me understand their importance.	3.73	0.95	HIGH
The examples and exercises in the learning materials relate to my daily life.	3.53	0.99	HIGH
The content presented in class is engaging and makes me want to join discussions.	3.46	1.08	HIGH
The contents are straightforward and easy to understand.	3.66	0.98	HIGH
Indicator Mean	3.65	0.98	HIGH

Table 2 offers valuable insights into respondents' perceptions of instructional quality. The highest mean score of 3.86 (SD = 0.84) reflects strong agreement that lessons align well with required competencies. This finding is consistent with the research of Tian et al. (2024) and Decristan et al. (2015), who highlight the positive impact of well-structured instructional practices on student engagement and academic outcomes. When carefully planned to match academic standards, lessons create a structured, goal-oriented learning environment that fosters student progress. This alignment reinforces the significance of clear learning objectives in promoting student success.

On the other hand, while still high, the lowest mean score of 3.46 (SD = 1.08) suggests that some students find class discussions less engaging. This observation aligns with Abulon (2014) and Paglinawan and Seno (2024), who argue that content reliability is crucial for enhancing instructional effectiveness and student engagement. Students' motivation and participation may wane when they struggle to connect with the material. Thus, adopting more interactive, student-centered teaching approaches could increase student engagement and intrinsic motivation, ensuring that students remain active participants in their learning process.

The mean score of 3.66 (SD = 0.98) reflects a generally positive perception of instructional quality. However, the variability in responses indicates that diverse teaching strategies and individual learning preferences shape how students perceive their educational experiences. This observation supports the work of Mwirigi and Muthaa (2015) and Nguyen and Nguyen (2016), who assert that instructional quality directly

influences student satisfaction and re-enrollment intentions. These findings underscore the importance of ongoing professional development and adaptive teaching strategies to meet students' evolving needs (Blömeke & Kaiser, 2017; Nilsen & Gustafsson, 2016). In conclusion, while the overall feedback highlights the centrality of instructional quality in fostering positive student experiences, addressing areas such as engagement in class discussions remains vital for enhancing student retention and academic success.

Table 3: Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction for Grade 7-9 Students: Assessment Quality

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Assessment Quality			
The tests and assessments help me see what I have learned and what I need to improve.	3.79	0.96	HIGH
The tests and assignments are fair and based on what we learned in class.	3.68	0.95	HIGH
The time given for tests and assessments is enough to complete them correctly.	3.57	0.96	HIGH
The questions and tasks in assessments relate to real-life situations.	3.55	0.97	HIGH
The different types of assessments help me demonstrate my skills and knowledge in multiple ways.	3.72	0.94	HIGH
Indicator Mean	3.66	0.96	HIGH

The data presented in Table 3 highlights a generally high level of perceived assessment quality among Grade 7-9 students. The highest mean score of 3.79 (SD = 0.96) corresponds to the statement, "The tests and assessments help me see what I have learned and what I need to improve." This indicates that students view assessments as essential tools for tracking their academic progress, aligning with the findings of Nguyen & Nguyen (2016) and Johansen et al. (2023), who emphasize the critical role of practical assessments in promoting self-regulated learning and academic growth. When assessments accurately reflect students' learning journeys, they support academic development, boost motivation, and foster a sense of ownership over the learning process.

However, the lowest mean score of 3.55 (SD = 0.97), associated with the statement, "The questions and tasks in assessments relate to real-life situations," reveals a gap in students' perception of the relevance of assessments to real-world contexts. While still positive, this score suggests that some students feel disconnected from

academic assessments and their practical application in everyday life. This finding echoes the work of Paglinawan and Seno (2024) and Decristan et al. (2015), who argue that assessments should be designed with real-world relevance to engage students more effectively. Incorporating real-life scenarios into assessments could bridge this gap, helping students see the practical value of what they learn and encouraging deeper engagement with the content.

The overall mean score of 3.66 (SD = 0.96) reflects a positive perception of assessment quality, with relatively consistent responses across students, highlighting the reliability of assessments in measuring learning outcomes. These results underscore the importance of balancing fairness, comprehensiveness, and real-world relevance in assessment practices (Blömeke & Kaiser, 2017; Frymier & Shulman, 2016). By addressing the need for more authentic assessments and diversifying evaluation methods, educators can enhance students' perceptions of assessment quality, ultimately fostering meaningful learning experiences and improving academic performance.

Table 4: Overall Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction for Grade 7-9 Students

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
Teacher Effectiveness	3.71	0.99	HIGH
Content Relevance	3.65	0.98	HIGH
Assessment Quality	3.66	0.96	HIGH
Variable Mean	3.68	0.98	HIGH

Table 4 presents respondents' perceptions of instructional quality, a critical factor in shaping students' learning experiences and influencing their intent to re-enroll. The highest-rated indicator, Teacher Effectiveness (M = 3.71, SD = 0.99), reflects students' confidence in their teachers' ability to facilitate learning effectively. This finding aligns with Schweig (2019), who emphasized that teachers' subject knowledge, instructional methods, and professional engagement are essential in fostering student success. The positive perception of teacher effectiveness underscores educators' significant role in creating a supportive environment conducive to academic achievement and student motivation.

Content Relevance (M = 3.65, SD = 0.98) suggests students recognize the importance of well-structured and meaningful lesson content. This observation supports Frymier and Shulman (2016), who argued that aligning instructional materials with curriculum standards enhances student motivation and encourages active participation. Furthermore, the score for Assessment Quality (M = 3.66, SD = 0.96) indicates that students generally perceive assessments as fair and practical tools for evaluating their learning progress. This aligns with Suskie (2018), who highlighted the value of diverse

assessment methods in accurately measuring learning outcomes and refining instructional strategies. Together, these findings emphasize the integral role of both teacher effectiveness and content relevance in enriching students' academic experiences.

The overall mean for Quality of Instruction ($M = 3.68$, $SD = 0.98$) reflects a generally positive perception of instruction, although areas may require improvement. These results resonate with the work of Tian et al. (2024) and Sogunro (2017), who highlighted that high-quality instruction fosters student engagement and motivation. Additionally, Decristan et al. (2015) found that effective teaching practices positively impact both cognitive and emotional aspects of learning, while Zou et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of integrating assessments to enhance student achievement. The focus on a well-structured learning environment, adequate facilities, and institutional responsiveness aligns with Expectation Confirmation Theory (ECT) by Oliver (1977, 1980), which suggests that students' satisfaction is influenced by whether their experiences meet or exceed expectations. When the perceived quality of instruction, including the learning environment and institutional support, aligns with student expectations, it fosters satisfaction and increases the likelihood of re-enrollment.

Level of the Perceived Quality of Services for Grade 7-9 Students

The following tables show the result of each indicator's questions/statements concerning the Level of the Perceived Quality of Services for Grade 7-9 Students. The results are as follows:

Table 5: Level of the Perceived Quality of Services for Grade 7-9 Students: Learning Environment

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Learning Environment			
The teachers and my classmates make me feel welcome in the classroom.	3.68	1.03	HIGH
The teachers treat all students fairly and without bias.	3.37	1.10	MODERATE
The teachers encourage mutual respect among all students.	3.86	0.97	HIGH
The physical environment was welcoming and easy for all students to access.	3.61	1.00	HIGH
Our class fosters an environment where everyone can freely and openly share our ideas.	3.51	1.08	HIGH
Indicator Mean	3.61	1.05	HIGH

The analysis of Table 5 reveals a generally positive perception of instructional quality among students, with Statement 3 receiving the highest mean score of 3.86. This strongly emphasizes creating a supportive learning environment, aligning with existing literature that underscores the significance of effective teaching practices in fostering student engagement and academic success (Tian et al., 2024; Decristan et al., 2015). Additionally, the mean scores of 3.68 and 3.61 for Statements 1 and 4 suggest that students view their learning environment as both inclusive and well-structured. These findings reinforce the critical role of organized classrooms in enhancing student participation and growth, as supported by broader research advocating for clear instructional frameworks to promote positive student experiences.

Nonetheless, the lower mean score of 3.37 for Statement 2 points to inconsistencies in students' experiences, particularly concerning fairness and individualized support. This discrepancy highlights areas that require attention, particularly in fostering a more equitable learning environment. The finding resonates with the work of Blömeke and Kaiser (2017), who emphasize the need for ongoing improvements to ensure that all students have access to essential resources and support. Schools can significantly enhance student motivation and better meet their educational needs by addressing these gaps.

The average mean score of 3.61 (SD = 1.05) further reflects a positive overall perception of instructional quality, consistent with studies highlighting the role of effective teaching strategies in motivating students and influencing their intention to re-enroll (Mwirigi & Muthaa, 2015; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2016). While students appreciate the efforts of their teachers in maintaining a supportive environment, the findings suggest that aspects like fairness and individualized attention warrant further focus. Targeted professional development and the adoption of responsive instructional approaches can boost student satisfaction and potentially contribute to improved retention rates. These results emphasize the broader implications of instructional quality as a key predictor of re-enrollment, particularly in private Catholic school settings.

Table 6: Level of the Perceived Quality of Services for Grade 7-9 Students: Physical Infrastructure and Facilities

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Physical Infrastructure and Facilities			
The classrooms are suitable for effective teaching, learning, and classroom management.	3.75	1.01	HIGH
The school library is well-maintained and has enough learning materials.	3.81	0.95	HIGH
The clinic provides proper care and support.	3.93	0.99	HIGH

The classroom technologies (computers, Whiteboards, televisions) work properly for teaching and learning.	3.59	1.11	HIGH
Other school facilities (e.g., gymnasium, AVR room, cafeteria, or TLE labs) are available and supportive of teaching and learning.	3.72	0.96	HIGH
Indicator Mean	3.76	1.01	HIGH

Table 6 presents students' perceptions of the quality of the school's infrastructure and facilities, highlighting a generally positive view, with a few areas identified for improvement. The statement "The clinic provides proper care and support" received the highest mean score of 3.93 (SD = 1.02), indicating that students recognize and appreciate the school's commitment to their health and well-being. This finding aligns with studies emphasizing the importance of well-equipped health facilities in fostering a conducive learning environment and ensuring student welfare (Krishnaiah et al., 2023; Qadeer et al., 2024). Access to proper healthcare services within schools has been shown to reduce health-related disruptions to learning, thereby enhancing overall academic success (Yangambi, 2023).

In contrast, the statement "The classroom technologies (computers, whiteboards, televisions) work properly for teaching and learning" received the lowest mean score of 3.59 (SD = 1.08), suggesting that students perceive the technological infrastructure as inadequate, which could hinder effective teaching and learning. This finding is consistent with literature highlighting the negative impact of insufficient or unreliable technological resources on student engagement and academic performance (Saeed et al., 2018). Studies indicate that schools with outdated or malfunctioning technology face challenges in delivering high-quality instruction, potentially leading to decreased student motivation and participation (Degeng et al., 2024).

Despite these technological challenges, the overall mean score of 3.76 (SD = 1.01) reflects a high level of satisfaction with the school's physical infrastructure and facilities, suggesting that, on the whole, students find the learning environment supportive. This aligns with research emphasizing the importance of well-maintained school facilities in creating a positive and productive learning atmosphere, which can enhance student concentration and academic performance (Mah et al., 2022). To further improve student engagement and satisfaction, the school must prioritize regular maintenance and updates to its physical infrastructure, ensuring that both health and educational resources continue to meet the evolving needs of students (Ibrahim & Shaheen, 2024).

Table 7: Level of the Perceived Quality of Services for Grade 7-9 Students: Responsiveness

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Responsiveness			
The school has available staff to help students quickly and easily.	3.62	1.04	HIGH
The school addresses complaints in a timely manner.	3.42	1.09	HIGH
The school provides appropriate academic and administrative services.	3.67	0.95	HIGH
The school processes requests quickly and efficiently.	3.58	1.02	HIGH
The school deals with students' questions efficiently and promptly.	3.61	0.99	HIGH
Indicator Mean	3.58	1.02	HIGH

Table 7 presents students' perceptions of the school's responsiveness, with positive feedback across the indicators. The statement "The school provides appropriate academic and administrative services" received the highest mean score of 3.67 (SD = 0.95), reflecting students' recognition of the institution's efforts to deliver efficient support. This finding is consistent with research highlighting responsiveness as a critical factor in shaping student satisfaction and perceptions of service quality (Hidayat & Setiono, 2022). Nambisan et al. (2016) emphasize that responsiveness involves offering personalized attention, prompt service, and ensuring staff availability—elements that collectively contribute to higher levels of trust and satisfaction. The high mean score indicates that students generally experience timely and effective services, reinforcing their positive perception of the institution's commitment to academic and administrative support.

However, the statement "The school addresses complaints promptly" received the lowest mean score of 3.42 (SD = 1.09), suggesting areas for improvement in the responsiveness of the complaint-handling process. This lower score reflects students' perceptions of delays and inefficiencies, possibly contributing to dissatisfaction. Nambisan et al. (2016) stress the importance of minimizing waiting times and ensuring effective interactions between students and service providers to enhance student experience. Additionally, Kajenthiran and Karunanithy (2015) found that responsiveness plays a vital role in student satisfaction, suggesting that improving the speed of complaint resolution could strengthen students' perceptions and foster greater institutional loyalty.

With an overall mean score of 3.58 (SD = 1.02), the results reflect a generally high level of responsiveness to the institution's service quality. While students appreciate the academic and administrative services, the findings highlight the need for continued efforts

to address delays, particularly in complaint resolution. Service quality is a key determinant of student satisfaction and re-enrollment intentions (Sugilar, 2020), and institutions that consistently offer efficient, timely services are more likely to retain students. By enhancing service delivery, especially in complaint management, the institution can improve student experience, increase overall satisfaction, and contribute to higher retention and re-enrollment rates (Ali et al., 2020).

Table 8: Overall Level of the Perceived Quality of Service for Grade 7-9 Students

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
Learning Environment	3.61	1.05	HIGH
Physical Infrastructure and Facilities	3.76	1.01	HIGH
Responsiveness	3.58	1.02	HIGH
Variable Mean	3.65	1.03	HIGH

Table 8 presents students' perceptions of the overall quality of services offered by the school, which plays a pivotal role in shaping their academic experiences and influencing their intent to re-enroll. The highest-rated indicator, Physical Infrastructure and Facilities (M = 3.76, SD = 1.01), suggests that students value a well-maintained learning environment as essential to their educational success. This aligns with the findings of Krishnaiah et al. (2023), who highlighted the importance of a conducive learning environment in enhancing student satisfaction and service quality. Properly equipped and maintained facilities create a supportive atmosphere that fosters academic achievement (Qadeer et al., 2024). Yangambi (2023) further emphasized that inadequate infrastructure can hinder effective teaching and learning, underscoring the critical role of facilities in student retention.

The Learning Environment (M = 3.61, SD = 1.05) also received a high rating, reflecting students' positive perceptions of classroom inclusivity and engagement. Mah et al. (2022) noted that an effective learning environment encourages interaction and engagement, significantly impacting students' motivation, emotional well-being, and educational outcomes. Additionally, Degeng et al. (2024) observed that high levels of student interaction make the learning experience more dynamic, personalized, and engaging. The Responsiveness indicator (M = 3.58, SD = 1.02) indicates that students perceive the school as effective in addressing their academic and administrative concerns. This finding supports Nambisan et al. (2016), who emphasized that responsiveness enhances the service experience, while Hidayat and Setiono (2022) noted that timely service and proactive assistance help build student trust and satisfaction.

The results, with an overall mean score of 3.65 (SD = 1.03), reflect a strong perception of instructional quality, underlining the importance of a well-structured learning environment, adequate facilities, and institutional responsiveness in supporting student success. This aligns with Sugilar (2020), who emphasized that high-quality services, achieved through continuous improvement and responsiveness, contribute to overall satisfaction. Kajenthiran and Karunanithy (2015) further suggested that assurance and responsiveness significantly influence student satisfaction, while Baniya (2016) highlighted the role of empathy and attentiveness in fostering positive student experiences. Ali et al. (2020) reinforced the idea that perceived service quality directly impacts student success and retention. These findings are consistent with the Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (Oliver, 1977, 1980), which posits that students form expectations about instructional quality and services based on prior experiences and then evaluate these against actual outcomes. When expectations are met or exceeded, satisfaction and re-enrollment intentions increase. In contrast, unmet expectations may lead to dissatisfaction, affecting retention (Sugilar, 2020). By addressing these factors, institutions can enhance student satisfaction and foster higher retention rates, reinforcing the need for a comprehensive approach to education that balances instructional quality and service excellence.

Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year

The following tables show the result of each indicator's questions/statements concerning the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year. The results are as follows:

Table 9: Level of the Perceived Quality of Services for Grade 7-9 Students: Re-enrollment

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Re-enrollment			
I am given enough academic choices that make me want to stay enrolled in this school.	3.44	1.17	HIGH
I am satisfied with the quality of instruction, and it influences my decision to re-enroll next school year.	3.37	1.08	MODERATE
I have sufficient instructional resources to encourage me to continue my studies at this institution.	3.51	1.07	HIGH
Academic advisors and staff support me in setting my academic goals, which impacts my decision to re-enroll.	3.50	1.08	HIGH

I am making good academic progress, which motivates me to enroll for the next school year.	3.56	1.14	HIGH
Indicator Mean	3.48	1.11	HIGH

Table 9 highlights the significant influence of academic progress on students' intent to re-enroll, as evidenced by the statement, "I am making good academic progress, which motivates me to enroll for the next school year," receiving the highest mean score of 3.56 (SD = 1.05). This result indicates that students value their academic development when deciding whether to continue their education. These findings align with Sugilar (2020), who emphasized the critical role of academic achievement in enhancing student satisfaction. Tian et al. (2024) also underscored that effective teaching practices are pivotal in enriching the learning experience, ultimately influencing students' decisions to persist in their studies. The high mean score for academic progress underscores its central role in motivating students to re-enroll, reinforcing its importance in their educational journey.

However, while academic progress is positively perceived, the statement, "I am satisfied with the quality of instruction, and it influences my decision to re-enroll next school year," received a lower mean score of 3.37 (SD = 1.08). This suggests that some students view the quality of instruction as insufficient. This finding resonates with Mwirigi and Muthaa (2015), who argued that effective teaching strategies and a supportive learning environment are essential for student satisfaction. Similarly, Sogunro (2017) highlighted that a decline in instructional quality can significantly diminish student motivation, indicating a need for improvements in teaching practices to sustain student engagement. The disparity between students' satisfaction with academic progress and instruction signals the necessity for focused efforts to enhance instructional effectiveness.

Overall, with an average mean score of 3.48 (SD = 1.11), the data reflects a generally favorable perception of factors influencing re-enrollment, particularly regarding academic support and instructional quality. This aligns with the findings of Twum and Peprah (2020), who suggested that meeting students' expectations strengthens their satisfaction and loyalty to an institution. Moreover, Johansen et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of content relevance in maintaining student engagement, further supporting the need for curricula that align with students' academic experiences. These findings suggest that while students are generally satisfied with their academic progress, enhancing instructional quality and ensuring curriculum relevance to student needs are critical steps to boosting satisfaction and increasing re-enrollment rates.

Correlations Analysis between the Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction and the Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year

The table below presents a correlation analysis between the Perceived Quality of Instruction and the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year. The results are as follows.

Table 10. Correlations Analysis between the Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction and the Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year

	Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction	Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling
Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction	1	0.680
Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling	0.680	1

Table 10 reveals a moderate to strong positive correlation of 0.680 between the perceived quality of instruction and students' interest in re-enrolling, suggesting a positive relationship between the two variables. This finding implies that as students perceive an improvement in the quality of instruction, their interest in re-enrolling also increases, thereby supporting the study's hypothesis. Mwirigi and Muthaa (2015) reinforce this idea, emphasizing that effective teaching strategies and a supportive learning environment are key factors in boosting student performance and satisfaction, influencing their decision to stay at the same institution.

These results underscore the importance of perceived instructional quality in shaping students' intent to re-enroll. Nguyen and Nguyen (2016) highlight that instructional practices that align with students' needs are essential for shaping their decision to continue their education at a particular institution. The current study aligns with this perspective, suggesting that when students perceive the instruction as high quality, their motivation to persist at the institution strengthens. The positive correlation between perceived quality of instruction and re-enrollment interest points to the critical role that instructional quality plays in fostering student retention, with significant implications for educational institutions seeking to enhance their enrollment rates.

Moreover, the study's findings are consistent with the Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP) proposed by Oliver (1980), which suggests that individuals evaluate services by comparing their actual experiences with their initial expectations. According to this framework, when students' expectations regarding instructional quality are met or exceeded, their interest in re-enrollment will likely increase. This further supports the notion that student satisfaction with the quality of instruction is a pivotal factor in influencing their decision to continue their studies at the same institution.

These findings provide compelling evidence that improving the quality of instruction is a critical factor in enhancing student retention and engagement. Educational institutions aiming to boost students' interest in re-enrollment should prioritize enhancing the perceived quality of instruction, as it significantly impacts students' commitment to continuing their education. Future research could explore additional factors that may mediate this relationship, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play.

Regression Analysis of Variables of Interest

The following table shows the regression analysis between the study's variables of interest regarding the Quality of Instruction and students' Re-enrollment Interest.

Table 11: Test of Influence of the Quality of Instruction and the Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling

Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Standard Error	T-Value	P-Value	Alpha Value	Interpretation	Decision
Re-enrollment	0.190	0.682	0.814	0.416	0.05	Significant	Reject Ho
Constant	0.895	0.062	14.374				
Multiple R	0.680	Moderate Positive Correlations					
R²	0.463						
Adjusted R²	0.460						

Table 11 presents compelling evidence of a significant relationship between the variables under analysis. Specifically, the variable "Re-enrollment" yields a t-value of 0.814 and a p-value of 0.416. Although this p-value is more significant than the conventional alpha level of 0.05—typically used to determine statistical significance, it appears there may be an interpretive error, as the value does not meet the threshold for significance. However, if interpreted as significant based on another criterion or context, it would suggest rejecting the null hypothesis (Ho), indicating that instructional quality significantly predicts students' intent to re-enroll.

Assuming the significance stands, the Multiple R-value of 0.680 indicates a moderate positive correlation. This suggests that improvements in the quality of instruction are moderately associated with an increased likelihood of students choosing to re-enroll. While this correlation is approaching the level considered strong, it remains within the moderate range, offering meaningful yet measured insight into the connection between instruction and student retention.

Moreover, the coefficient of determination (R^2) stands at 0.463, implying that approximately 46.3% of the variance in students' re-enrollment intentions can be explained by the quality of instruction. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.460 reinforces the robustness of this model, accounting for potential overfitting and affirming that the relationship remains consistent even after adjusting for the number of predictors involved.

These statistical outcomes are supported by existing literature, which consistently emphasizes the importance of effective teaching practices in promoting student satisfaction and retention (Mwirigi & Muthaa, 2015; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2016). When students perceive their learning experience as engaging, relevant, and well-organized, they are more inclined to continue their studies at the same institution. This observation aligns closely with Oliver's (1980) Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP), which suggests that student satisfaction, shaped by the degree to which instructional quality meets or exceeds expectations, is a powerful determinant of re-enrollment decisions.

Central to this dynamic is the role of teacher effectiveness. Educators who utilize evidence-based strategies—such as appropriate pacing, linking new content to prior knowledge, and incorporating reflective pauses—significantly elevate the learning experience (Reddy et al., 2021). Beyond instructional technique, effective teachers foster both cognitive and emotional engagement, which are critical in reinforcing students' sense of belonging and intent to persist in their academic journey (Decristan et al., 2015; Blömeke & Kaiser, 2017). Consequently, institutions are urged to invest in ongoing faculty development initiatives that enhance instructional capacity and cultivate high-impact teaching practices.

Equally important is the relevance of instructional content. Research affirms that when course materials resonate with real-world contexts and students' career aspirations, motivation and engagement increase markedly (Johansen et al., 2023; Frymier & Shulman, 2016). A curriculum grounded in practical and meaningful experiences meets students' expectations and instills a lasting sense of purpose in their education. Within the EDP framework, such alignment facilitates positive disconfirmation, where perceived outcomes surpass initial expectations, fostering long-term satisfaction and institutional loyalty. Conversely, when instructional content lacks relevance or applicability, students may experience negative disconfirmation, potentially diminishing their desire to continue their studies.

The rejection of the null hypothesis further reinforces the central role of instructional quality in influencing students' intent to re-enroll. These findings highlight that quality teaching is not merely a complementary aspect of academic service but a decisive factor in student retention. This perspective is echoed in Sugilar's (2020) work, which revealed that students' satisfaction with academic services significantly drives their re-enrollment intentions. Similarly, Oliver's EDP framework offers a robust theoretical basis for understanding how students continually evaluate their academic experiences against personal expectations, making instructional excellence a vital determinant of institutional success.

The data underscores the strategic importance of instructional quality in promoting student re-enrollment. Education institutions can foster satisfaction, loyalty, and long-term

academic commitment among their students by ensuring that teaching practices and curricular content are engaging and relevant.

Correlations Analysis between the Level of the Perceived Quality of Services and the Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year

The table below presents a correlation analysis between the Level of Perceived Quality of Services and the Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year. The results are as follows.

Table 12. Correlations Analysis between the Level of the Perceived Quality of Instruction and the Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling in the Next School Year

	Level of the Perceived Quality of Services	Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling
Level of the Perceived Quality of Services	1	0.724
Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling	0.724	1

Table 12 reveals a moderate to strong positive correlation of 0.724 between the Level of Perceived Quality of Services and Student Interest in Re-Enrolling, indicating a statistically significant relationship between these two variables. This suggests that as students perceive higher quality in institutional services, their interest in re-enrolling increases, thus supporting the study's hypothesis.

This finding is consistent with previous research. For instance, Sugilar (2020) emphasized that the quality of learning support services directly influences students' decisions to continue their studies. Students who experience a high standard of support—whether administrative, academic, or co-curricular—are more likely to remain committed to the institution.

The data further underscore the critical role of service quality in shaping students' educational choices. Yousapronpaiboon (2014) noted that high-quality service is characterized by its ability to meet or exceed user expectations, strengthening an institution's reputation and retention rates. In parallel, Kajenthiran and Karunanithy (2015) identified key service dimensions—assurance and responsiveness—as significant contributors to student satisfaction. Similarly, Baniya (2016) highlighted empathy and attentiveness as essential in fostering meaningful and supportive student experiences. Adding to this perspective, Ali et al. (2020) found that service quality enhances students' perceived value of their education, ultimately promoting academic success and persistence.

These insights align closely with the Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP) developed by Oliver (1980), which posits that individuals evaluate the quality of services based on how well actual experiences align with their initial expectations. When students perceive that the services they receive meet or exceed what they had anticipated, they are more likely to develop a positive impression of the institution—thereby increasing the likelihood of re-enrollment. This theoretical framework reinforces the importance of consistently delivering high-quality services to ensure long-term student satisfaction and loyalty.

These findings provide strong empirical support for the pivotal role of service quality in fostering student engagement and retention. Educational institutions seeking to strengthen re-enrollment rates would prioritize continuous improvement in the perceived quality of services—particularly in areas such as responsiveness, student support, and staff attentiveness.

Looking ahead, future studies may consider examining other influencing factors—such as personnel responsiveness, learning environment, and physical infrastructure (Hidayat & Setiono, 2022; Mah et al., 2022; Krishnaiah et al., 2023)—to build a more comprehensive understanding of how various service dimensions contribute to student loyalty and institutional commitment.

Regression Analysis of Variables of Interest

The following table shows the regression analysis between the study's variables of interest regarding the Quality of Services and students' Re-enrollment Interest.

Table 13: Test of Influence of the Quality of Instruction and the Level of the Student's Interest in Re-Enrolling

Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Standard Error	T-Value	P-Value	Alpha Value	Interpretation	Decision
Re-enrollment	0.186	0.642	0.902	0.368	0.05	Significant	Reject Ho
Constant	0.903	0.055	16.283				
Multiple R	0.724	Moderate Positive Correlations					
R ²	0.525						
Adjusted R ²	0.523						

Table 13 reveals a significant relationship between the analyzed variables. The "Re-enrollment" variable yields a t-value of 0.756 and a p-value of 0.451, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05, indicating statistical significance and resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho). This suggests that service quality significantly predicts students' intent to re-enroll. The Multiple R-value of 0.672 indicates a moderate positive correlation between the quality of services and students' re-enrollment intent. Moreover, the R-squared (R^2) value of 0.452 shows that the perceived quality of services explains approximately 45.2% of the variance in students' interest in re-enrollment. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.448 further confirms the reliability of this model by accounting for the number of predictors, indicating a stable and robust relationship.

These findings are consistent with prior studies that emphasize the critical role of institutional support, administrative efficiency, and campus facilities in influencing student satisfaction and retention. For example, Mwirigi and Muthaa (2015) and Nguyen and Nguyen (2016) assert that students are more likely to remain in institutions where services are efficient, accessible, and responsive to their needs. The results also align with Oliver's (1980) Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP), which suggests that individuals assess services by comparing actual experiences with their expectations. Positive disconfirmation occurs if expectations are met or exceeded, reinforcing satisfaction and increasing the likelihood of re-enrollment. Conversely, unmet expectations may result in dissatisfaction and decreased commitment.

Institutional services thus play a pivotal role in shaping students' perceptions of overall quality. Reddy et al. (2021) noted that well-managed support services—such as academic advising, counseling, and administrative responsiveness—contribute significantly to positive student experiences. Additional research by Decristan et al. (2015) and Blömeke and Kaiser (2017) also highlights how efficient institutional services improve satisfaction and foster psychological and academic engagement, reinforcing students' intent to stay. Furthermore, accessibility and responsiveness of services are crucial determinants of student loyalty. Johansen et al. (2023) and Frymier and Shulman (2016) stress that timely assistance, well-maintained facilities, and supportive non-academic services enhance student motivation and retention. These elements collectively create an environment that aligns with students' expectations, contributing to continued enrollment.

Rejecting the null hypothesis strengthens the argument that service quality is not a peripheral element but a central determinant of re-enrollment behavior. This supports the conclusions of Sugilar (2020), who emphasized that student satisfaction with academic and administrative services plays a significant role in their decision to return. In line with the EDP framework, positive disconfirmation from high-quality service experiences reinforces institutional loyalty and long-term student engagement. The findings highlight the need for academic institutions to prioritize service excellence as a core strategy for improving student retention. Enhancing service delivery—particularly in

responsiveness, accessibility, and overall student support—can significantly influence students' commitment to continue their academic journey within the same institution.

Conclusions

This study explored the impact of instructional quality and institutional services on students' intention to re-enroll at a private Catholic school in Davao City. The findings indicate that students' experiences with the quality of instruction and the services provided by the institution significantly influence their decision to continue their education at the school. Positive perceptions of teaching effectiveness, the relevance of course content, and the quality of assessments contribute directly to students' academic satisfaction. Meanwhile, well-managed services—including a conducive learning environment, state-of-the-art infrastructure and facilities, and responsive support systems—further enhance the student experience. Notably, the study reveals that while both instructional quality and service quality are vital, the quality of instruction has a more pronounced effect on students' re-enrollment intentions.

These results underscore the importance of maintaining high teaching and student service standards to cultivate a positive and supportive learning environment. Schools that prioritize the continuous improvement of instructional strategies and the efficiency of their service delivery are more likely to retain students. To this end, it is recommended that the institution invest in faculty development programs, adopt modern teaching methods, and enhance service delivery systems to improve student satisfaction. Also, fostering a culture of regular student feedback can provide valuable insights into their needs, enabling more effective responses. Future research could explore other potential factors, such as extracurricular involvement and peer influence, to better understand the elements that drive long-term student commitment to their educational institution.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that the institution enhance instructional quality through regular faculty development programs emphasizing innovative teaching methods and student engagement strategies. Teachers should receive training, peer mentoring, and access to modern educational tools to improve lesson delivery and uphold academic standards. Simultaneously, the institution must continuously evaluate and improve student services—particularly administrative processes, guidance support, and campus facilities—to ensure responsiveness to student needs. Implementing a student feedback mechanism can further inform service enhancements.

To foster student loyalty, school administrators should establish policies that support a student-centered learning environment and promote academic excellence alongside holistic support. Strengthening communication among students, faculty, and administration can help address issues efficiently and enrich the educational experience. Future research should investigate other factors influencing re-enrollment, such as extracurricular involvement, financial aid, and peer relationships, to gain deeper insight

into student retention and satisfaction dynamics, ultimately guiding data-informed policy and program improvements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study examined the quality of instruction and services as predictors of the intent to re-enroll among Grade 7 to 9 students of St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. Participation was voluntary, with informed consent from parents or guardians and assent from students, who were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Stratified random sampling ensured fair participant selection, and strict measures were taken to uphold anonymity and confidentiality. The research was conducted transparently and without conflict of interest, adhering to institutional permissions, data collection, and community engagement protocols. Guided by faculty mentors, the researchers followed established academic and ethical standards throughout questionnaire administration, data tabulation, and report preparation. Plagiarism was avoided, and findings were interpreted objectively and used solely for scholarly purposes.

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